

Application development using the Brick framework

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Abstract

Unstructured operational phase-related data is an obstacle on a way to portable and scalable building maintenance applications. For the development of any application from a mobile game to a complex distributed web system developer tools and standards are required. When it comes to the operational phase of construction, there is a lot of static data produced in previous stages and unstructured data for building maintenance which is usually handled by facility managers. One of the most efficient abstractions for handling heterogeneous maintenance data is a Resource Description Framework (RDF) in general and Brick ontology in particular. Brick is a community-driven and open-source ontology whose domain is in Building Management Systems and HVAC equipment. Structured by Brick maintenance data can be used in applications for energy analysis.

This master thesis is an attempt to build a data analysis application for the operational stage of construction that will use both static and structured maintenance data for visualizing the indoor environment. The domain of thesis research and tools that were used for development avoid any proprietary formats and software. The application itself was built in a self-sustainable way to keep the opportunity of including it in a complex distributed system open based on Docker containers.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/EL--wmVPypQ>

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